

Uploaded to this community you will find both our report on how beer foam decay and structure contribute to beer quality, and the data that led to the report.

We investigated 3 beers; Tuborg Classic, Tuborg Grøn and Tuborg Guld. For each of these beers is an upload with the photographs from one test. These consist of photographs taken of the beer foam every ten seconds for the duration of five minutes. In reality we did 3 tests of each beer, but we could not upload everything to Zenodo due to upload limits.

We analyzed these photographs using Fiji software. We have uploaded CVS files of the results from Fiji analysis for each test of each beer. These each consist of a bubble count, a list of bubble areas, and in some cases a calculated mean bubble area and standard deviation of bubble area.

Lastly, we logged the beer foam height and graphed it as a function of time for all tests of all beers. An excel file with those data logs and graphs has also been uploaded to our community in order to make it easy to trace back every calculation and result.